

Autonomy of sport and the state intervention Case of provisional sport committees in Morocco

Abderrazak El AKARI

Professor of organizations management, Royal Institute for training youth and sport managers, Morocco

Abstract : In a context of openness accustomed to a strong involvement of civil society in the decision-making process of public affairs, any action emanating from the State will be badly perceived and considered as an interference, an abuse of power and finally, a return to an authoritarian State system omnipresent in the socio-economic sphere which stifles all initiatives.

It is in this context that the reaction of the Olympic and sports movement (O.S.M.) to the appointment by the ministry in charge of sport of civil servants in place of an elected federal office in the management of a given sport discipline must be appreciated. Although their field of intervention is regulated and limited in time and space, it nevertheless continues to provoke strong reactions, indignation and often protests for this interference in a field that is used to being managed by the sports and Olympic movement.

Thus, a power struggle emerges between the State interested in getting its hands on a domain deemed sensitive with important socio-economic and political ramifications and on the other hand the M.S.O. which seeks, by all means at its disposal, to preserve the autonomy of the management of sports affairs from any state or other interference.

This article raises questions relating to the concept of power within organizations, the management of conflicts between the MOS and the state, the reasons justifying the intervention of the latter and the instruments used by the state to ensure the perpetuation of control over the sports domain. It will be a question of analysing the course of the provisional committees, as a means of direct intervention by the state, during the period 1979-2020, using, as methodological tools, the analysis of official documentation, interviews with sports officials and the author's actual participation in the management of some of these committees.

Keywords: Autonomy, Provisional Committee, power, sport.

I. Introduction

In November 2013, a few weeks before Morocco was to organize the first edition of the Mondialitournament, the International Federation of Football Amateur (FIFA) decided not to recognize the new status of the Royal Moroccan Football Federation (RMFF), due to the many irregularities that marred the Extraordinary General Assembly, in particular the failure of the RMFF to comply with its duty to follow FIFA's directives (art. 13, para. 1a of the FIFA Statutes).

In order to avoid FIFA's sanctions, which could have negative repercussions on football activities and the image of the Kingdom, Morocco sent a delegation made up of representatives of the RMFF and the Ministry of Sport a week later to reassure FIFA of the democratic nature of its elections, and the absence of interference by the State in the affairs of this federation.

Among the points contested by FIFA representatives during the discussions, was the fact that the draft statutes of the Moroccan federation, which are certainly in line with the Moroccan sports code (law 30-09), are in contradiction with certain constants of the FIFA model statutes, in particular the fact that a member of the administration sits on the federal board that is supposed to be elected. This article has been interpreted by FIFA representatives as a breach of Article 17 of the FIFA Statutes.

This incident or institutional crisis, reflects one of the issues/sources of conflict in the field of sport, namely the confrontation between the legal order created by international sports organizations and its applicability in the national territory, which already has its own norms. This incident also made those responsible for sport in Morocco, notably the Football Federation and the Ministry of Sport, aware of the extent of the power of international sports organizations, which are very wary of any act of interference by the State in the attributions devolved to national sports federations.

It is well known that international sports organizations, such as the International Olympic Committee (IOC) and FIFA, react to all acts of interference in the internal affairs of federations. The most frequent cases concern repeated ministerial interventions in the composition of NOCs and NFs or in their elections. For the same reason, the IOC suspended the NOC of IRAQ in 2008 and the NOC of Panama in 2007, and refused to recognise the elections of new leaders of the NOC of Albania in 2009. In October 2015, the IOC decided to suspend the Kuwaiti Olympic Committee because of the government's interference in its management by imposing a new sports law contrary to the fundamental principles governing the Olympic movement.

Also, the IOC unanimously decided on 26 October 2019, during its General Assembly, to suspend the International Boxing Federation due to ethical, refereeing and governance issues.

Similarly, FIFA "suspended the football federations of Albania and Madagascar in 2008. It threatened to suspend the Spanish federation whose government wanted to bring forward the elections; finally the latter backed down for fear that the Spanish team would not be able to participate in Euro 2008." (Chappelet. 2010. 23)

II. Theoretical approach of power in organizations

Before specifying the contours of provisional sports management, it is preferable to present a definition of the concepts that will be used throughout this article.

The notion of provisional sports committee refers to a derogation to the general rule that consists in delegating the power to manage sport (animation, supervision, training, competition management, etc.) to the sport and Olympic movement, to the benefit of State officials according to precise legal rules, instead of an elected office for a limited mission and duration.

Concerning sport, we will retain the following definition, presented by the Council of Europe in its Sport Charter (2007), which seems broad and flexible enough to reflect this diversity. Sport" means all forms of physical activity which, through organized or unorganized participation, have as their objective the expression or improvement of physical and mental fitness, the development of social relations or the achievement of competitive results at all levels.

A. Power in organizations

The question of power within organizations has long been one of the major concerns of researchers, particularly in the field of organizational management, to such an extent that it has become a catch-all, polysemic concept, making it difficult to give a precise definition.

Similarly, various currents of thought have tried to present answers that make it possible to understand and explain the transformations of public action with the fragmentation, complexity and uncertainty that increasingly characterize the relations between the various players in the public sphere. It is clear that the control of public action is no longer the prerogative of the state alone, which was previously the architect of a hierarchical order.

The first research works tried to understand both public and private organizations, from the point of view of the mechanisms, the used tools, the decision-making process, the relations between the actors, the exercised power, but also to identify the multiple dysfunctions within the organization. The American school of thought has tried to conduct empirical research on the functioning of organizations and on institutional dynamics (Mintzberg, 1983).

Nevertheless, this very simplistic perception of public action has been strongly criticised, as it presents the organization as a rational structure and does not take into consideration the vagaries of decision-making processes and the specificities of public policy actors and their interaction modes.

Among the interested researchers in the mechanisms of institutional change, Crozier. According to him, the concept of power is defined as "the capacity for certain individuals or groups to act on other individuals or groups...Thus, power can only develop through the exchange between the actors involved in a given relationship; it is, therefore, a relationship of exchange and negotiation in which at least two people are involved". (Crozier and Friedberg.1977.15)

For Crozier, the actor does not have clear and coherent objectives; in fact he changes them, and adapts them according to his results. He always has a certain activity, even in passivity: his behavior always has a meaning, having an offensive aspect (improving his situation) and a defensive aspect (maintaining his margin of freedom). It is in this sense that Crozier and Friedberg conceived the notion of collective learning "through which a group of actors, as part of a system of action, learn new patterns of play, with their affective, cognitive and relational components." (Crozier & Friedberg, 1981, 341).

Within an organization, the instrument of play develops which "reconciles freedom and constraint. The player remains free, but if he wants to win, he must adopt a rational strategy according to the nature of the game and respect its rules. This means that he must accept, for the advancement of his interests, the constraints imposed on him. If it is a cooperative game, as is always the case in an organization, the product of the game will be the common outcome sought by the organization." (Crozier & Friedberg.1981. 97).

Nevertheless, this game instrument revolves around the notion of power which "is a relationship and not an attribute of the actors... It is linked to the relationship of exchange, of negotiation. It is a relationship that is goal-oriented, non-transitive and reciprocal, but unbalanced. It is a power relationship from which one can gain more than the other, but where one is never totally powerless against the other. It is therefore necessary to study the spatial, temporal and social framework in order to measure the strengths of each, or the constraints that weigh on them." (Crozier & Friedberg, 1981, 56).

The organization in this sense has an important role to play in trying to regulate the course of power relations, affecting the ability of its members to play and conditioning their will by setting sufficiently relevant and important stakes. Not all of an actor's resources are relevant or mobilisable.

Crozier and Friedberg show that the control of uncertainties is a source of power. Even in a controlled social system, every actor has a margin of freedom. Every social relationship is a power relationship, there can be no structure without power and no power without structure. There is never one ideal solution, but several solutions.

Generally speaking, the sources of power are:

- the possession of a skill or specialty,
- the relationship between the organization and its environment,
- the control of internal communication,
- the use of organizational rules. "(Crozier and Friedberg, 1981 p. 72).

In the same vein, power is an absolute notion that only materializes through negotiations and areas of uncertainty created at the margins of the normalized system.

Other researchers have tried to further develop the concept of power. Maillet (1989) sees power as a means of achieving the desired result, by virtue of an unbalanced relationship between two actors. This definition emphasizes the result as well as the means used to achieve it. Goguelin (1989) defines the 'real power' of an individual as the sum of three powers (the *de jure* power officially attached to a status; the *de facto* power which is attached to the possession of a competence and the recognition power whose expression is charisma).

According to McClelland, furthermore "power appears as an ability for an individual to have an impact on the thoughts, actions or feelings of others or on the course of events and to prevent his own thoughts, actions or feelings from being changed by others in a way he does not wish". (McClelland, 1970, 6)

B. The Sport Movement's Relationship with Governments

It must be recognized that during the 20th century, sport developed in the form of non-profit associations with an autonomy towards governmental bodies.

The autonomy of sport draws its resources from the writings of the Olympic movement, notably its charter: "According to the Coubertinian conception, still valid for the IOC, its members are independent of their governments and represent the Olympic movement in their country. They are, therefore, politically autonomous and this autonomy is often reinforced by their financial independence. (Chappelet, 2010, 11)

According to Chappelet, who conducted a study regarding the autonomy of sport, this notion represents "the possibility for non-profit, non-governmental sports organizations to:

- "freely establish, modify and interpret appropriate rules to their sport without undue political or economic influence,
- Democratically choose their leaders without interference from states or third parties;
- To obtain adequate public or third party funds without disproportionate obligations;
- To carry out chosen objectives and activities with these funds without strong external constraints;
- To develop, in negotiation with the public authorities, legitimate and proportionate standards for the achievement of these objectives. (Chappelet, 2010, 51)

The question of the autonomy of sports organizations became a topical issue at the beginning of the 1980s with the emergence of questions of television broadcasting rights, the principle of free competition, violence in stadiums, etc. To mark their unwavering point of view and their attachment to autonomy, literature relating to the IOC states that "autonomy is a necessity for the Olympic and Sports Movement, as it guarantees the preservation of the values of sport, the integrity of competitions, the motivation and participation of volunteers, the education of young people and the contribution to the well-being of all, women, men and children, thus contributing to its credibility and legitimacy." (Chappelet, 2010, 14)

According to the IOC, sports activities have certain particularities that make it difficult or even abnormal to apply the rules of common law, in particular "the specificity of sports activities and the rules that apply to them, such as the organization of separate competitions for men and women, the limitation of the number of participants in competitions or the need to ensure the uncertainty of results and to preserve the competitive balance between clubs participating in the same competition. Also the

specificity of sports structures, in particular the autonomy and diversity of sports organizations, the pyramid structure of competitions from recreational to high-level sport, the structured solidarity mechanisms between the different levels and stakeholders, the organization of sport on a national basis and the principle of a single federation for each sport." (Chappelet. 2009. 18)

III. The main actors of sport in Morocco

The content of Law 30-09 on Physical Education and Sports, shows the existence of three entities with a preponderant power in the animation and supervision of sport in Morocco:

- The Ministry in charge of sport
- The Moroccan National Olympic Committee;
- The sports federations.

A. The Moroccan National Olympic Committee

The Moroccan legislator has not omitted to devote an entire chapter to the Moroccan National Olympic Committee, whose mission is to

- Ensure the promotion of sport;
- -Contribute to the preparation of athletes and ensure, in agreement with the administration, the participation of Morocco in various international sports events...

Among the important innovations of this law:

- Respect for the principles of good governance, in particular the obligation imposed on the CNOM to "be composed of members elected from among their members by the executive committees of national sports federations" (Art 41). Another novice: "any member who ceases to be a member of the executive committee of a sports federation, loses his or her status as a member of the CNOM" (Art 42)
- Encourage the creation of regional Olympic committees (Art 41 Para 4) in order to avoid excessive centralization and allow the CNOM to participate effectively in the promotion of the noble values of Olympism.
- Creation within the CNOM of the Chamberarbitral du sport, which is entrusted to pronounce, at the request of the parties concerned, on any dispute arising from the organization or practice of physical and sports activities between licensed sportsmen and sportswomen, sports associations, sports companies, sports federations, regional leagues and professional leagues" (Art 44) This article is crucially important because it fills a legal vacuum and finds a way to take into consideration the specificity of the sports field.
- Create a National Paralympic Committee capable of managing all aspects related to the participation of Morocco in international competitions organized under the aegis of the International Paralympic Committee (IPC).

B. The Sports Federations

A careful reading of the content of Law 30-09 reveals broad prerogatives granted to sports federations, for the socio-historical reasons mentioned above. Nevertheless, it is a freedom rationalized by preconditions imposed by the administrative authority in charge.

The legislator mentioned for the first time that "Sports federations participate in the execution of a public service mission. They also participate in the organization of sports training and refereeing activities of the discipline they govern according to their statutes and contribute to the definition of the content and pedagogical methods of this training" (Art 22).

Thus, the essential missions of sports federations are:

- To exercise disciplinary power over athletes and associations and leagues (Art 24);
- There can only be one authorized federation per sport discipline (Art 25);
- To issue licenses to members of associations for the practice of the sports disciplines for which they are responsible... and to issue authorizations to national sportsmen and sportswomen as provided for by international regulations to participate in sports competitions (Art 28);
- To organize competitions between leagues, associations, profit-making sports societies, athletes or players... they participate in the organization of sports training in the discipline they govern (Art 70);
- to receive from individuals and any legal person under public or private law, aid, donations and subsidies, in particular in the form of financial assistance and the provision of the supervisory and teaching staff necessary for the preparation of selections and the promotion of sportsmen and women (Art. 82).
- Generally speaking, according to their particular statutes, the purpose of sports federations is to:

- To bring together leagues and sports associations;
- Defend the moral and material interests of the sport discipline;
- To ensure the respect of the laws and regulations of the sport discipline;
- To organize, encourage, promote, develop, popularize and regulate the practice of the sport;
- To organize conferences, courses, training courses, seminars and any cultural or other activity to popularize and develop the practice of the sport;
- To manage and direct the competitions of the sport in conformity with the standards established by the international federations.
- Among the innovations brought by the new law compared to the former repealed text:
- Integrate the principles of good governance in its statutes (Guarantee the democratic functioning of the federation / Access to sport for all / Limit the term of office of the president to two successive terms" (Art 23)
- Provide for the notion of empowerment granted by regulation in order to benefit from the advantages provided for in their favor (Art 25).

C. Ministry of Youth and Sports (MJS)

The legislator has given the Ministry of Youth and Sports a prominent place in the field of sports by granting it wide-ranging prerogatives in the area of popularization, and also to ensure an honorable presentation of Morocco on the international scene. Generally, the devolved attributions to the department of sport are:

- The popularization and supervision of sports activities;
- The promotion of high level activities;
- The coordination, follow-up and control of the activities of federations, leagues and sports associations;
- The elaboration of programs concerning the infrastructure of sports facilities.
- Similarly, it is the responsibility of the State to ensure the socio-economic integration of high-level athletes as a sign of recognition of their efforts.
- Law 30.09 confirms this assertion through the following components:
 - Training/coaching/education
 - Development and social integration
 - Effective and consultative management
- Control and monitoring
- Power of supervision.

All these factors justify a strong presence of the State, thus "Physical education and the practice of sports activities are interesting, and their development is a public service mission". Therefore, the State, according to the preamble of the law, is:

- Responsible for the development of the sport movement and assumes its supervision and control,
- It must "contribute to and ensure, in coordination with the Moroccan National Olympic Committee and the relevant sports federations, the training of elite athletes, the preparation of national sports teams and their participation in international sports competitions".

1. Reasons justifying the intervention of the MJS

The reasons that justify the intervention of public authorities in the field of sport can be summarized as follows:

Failure of the sport movement to assume the mission of promoting sport.

Poor results recorded on the international sports scene.

Concerning the first aspect, although the sport movement has been delegated the power to manage all aspects of the sport field, and the human and financial means put at its disposal, it is necessary to recognize, through the official figures, the modesty of its intervention and its inability to enlarge the base of sport practitioners. (El akari.2015. 129)

Based on the notion of subsidiarity, the public authorities are obliged to intervene to fill these identified gaps.

The second aspect is crucially important, and following the example of developed or developing countries, Morocco is particularly interested in ensuring a strong presence on the international sports scene, given its beneficial effects on the image and influence of the State.

The administration in charge of the country, uses, to good effect, the sports performances achieved to justify the efficiency of the applied sports system, sometimes at the expense of certain undemocratic practices of the federal offices, following in this sense the well-known adage: how can one change a winning team?

It should be noted that the crises that have shaken Moroccan sport, have their roots in the poor performances achieved at the international level. For example:

- 1979: The defeat of the national football team in front of its Algerian counterpart led to the dissolution of the federal bureau and the appointment of an administrative committee
- 1990: The collective resignation of the Federal Handball Board due to the lack of means to represent Morocco in the African Championship pushed the Administration in charge of sport to appoint a provisional committee;
- 1992 The elimination of the national basketball team from the African championship, whose leaders had failed to provide their team with a regulation uniform, prompted the Ministry to suspend the annual subsidy that was allocated to it;
- 1993: The case of the Moroccan athlete Ettaqui, suspected of having facilitated the victory of the Algerian Morcelli at the World Athletics Championship in Stuttgart, precipitated the dissolution of the B-F and the appointment of a provisional committee
- 1994: Elimination, described as humiliating, of the national team at the 1994 football world cup in the USA, led to the dissolution of the B-F and the appointment of a provisional committee to manage its affairs.
- 2008: Defeat of the national football team precipitated the dissolution of the federal bureau and the election of a new bureau.

2. Intervention tools of the MJS

These tools are multiple and adapted according to the context of relations between the State-sports and Olympic movements, which vary from regular information on the actions carried out by the federation and which can go as far as the withdrawal of accreditation and the designation of a provisional committee to replace an elected bureau.

The delegation of power from the State to the sport movement is governed by conditions that can be flexible or strict depending on the nature of the situation between the reinforcement of State structures within the framework of the "Welfare State" or the progressive regression of its domains of intervention while being satisfied with the regalian functions of the "State-Gendarme". This supervision of the sport movement often takes different forms:

- Presence of the Ministry's representative as an advisor during official meetings of the federation (Art 27 law 30-09)
- Post-audit of financial reports to verify the accuracy and veracity of the accounting information provided and its conformity with the texts in force;
- Requiring, for the granting of the annual subsidy, to provide a certificate from an auditor confirming the realization of the federation's operations. Taking into account the fact that most federations depend on the subsidy granted by the Ministry, which constitutes an instrument of pressure to orient the strategic choices of a sports federation.
- Direct intervention through the use of Article 31 of Law 30-09 on the appointment of a provisional committee.

IV. Case study of provisional sports committees

We will analyze, as a case study, the crisis situation within sports organizations, obliging the public authorities in Morocco to intervene to remove an elected bureau and appoint, in parallel, a provisional committee made up of state officials.

It is important to note that the structure of the provisional committee existed before the new law 30-09. We, therefore, propose to analyze this form of public authority intervention at the time of the repealed law (06-87) and under the new law 30-09.

A. Provisional committees under the repealed law 06-87

The appointment of a provisional committee is closely linked to the application of article 22 of the repealed law 06-87 relating to physical education and sports, which stipulates that "the federation's authorization may be withdrawn in the event of non-compliance with the operating rules set out in its statutes or violation of the legislation or regulations applicable to it or when the federation's operation or activities are prejudicial to the sport in question, the Administration may dissolve the federal governing body and take all useful measures in the interest of the sport concerned, and, in particular, appoint a provisional committee whose mission is to ensure the management of the federation until the meeting of the General Assembly, the date of which the provisional committee fixes within a maximum period of one year from the date of dissolution of the governing body of the federation concerned. "

This empowerment is based on the existence of statutory provisions guaranteeing the democratic functioning and transparency of the management of sports federations.

Generally speaking, the appointment of a provisional committee is the result of a combination of unpleasant events. Starting with the emergence of internal conflicts within the federation, either between the members of the elected bureau or with the representatives of the clubs who disapprove of the opacity of its mode of governance, passing through the publication in the national press of "dirty laundry" followed by an exchange of criticisms and accusations between the warring parties. They succeeded in exerting strong pressure on parliamentarians to present oral and written questions demanding the intervention of the minister in charge of sport and above all the application of article 22 of the repealed law.

Table 1: Chronology of provisional committees in Morocco

		Date of nomination	Sports discipline	Quality of personality	Reasons for appointment	Date of end
1	1	1979	Football	civil servant	National team defeat	1986
	2	Oct. 1979	Basketball	civil servant	Conflict between clubs and Executive board	Déc. 1981
	3	1981	Athletics	civil servant	Conflict between clubs and E.B	1982
	4	1981	Basketball	civil servant	Conflict between clubs and E.B	1983
2	5	July 1991	Handball	civil servant	Collective resignation of the E.B	Sep 1992
	6	Sept 1994	Football	Sport Personality	Bad results in World Cup	Dec 1999
	7	1996	Cycling	civil servant	Bad results Tournament in Italy	2003
	8	1996	Handball	Sport Personality	Resignation of the President and conflict between clubs E.B	1998
	9	Sep 2000	Athletics	Sport Personality	Resignation of the President	04 Dec. 2006
	10	Sep2000	Taekwondo	civil servant	Conflict between clubs and E.B	2001
	11	Sep 2000	Fencing	civil servant	Conflict between clubs and E.B	25Sep2003
	12	August2002	Wrestling	civil servant	Conflict between clubs and E.B	August 2003
	13	2004	Fencing	civil servant	Conflict clubs and E.B	August 2005
	14	March 2006	Cycling	civil servant	Conflict clubs and E.B-	March 2008
	15	2009	Bodybuilding	civil servant	Conflict clubs and E - B	June2011
3	16	5 Jul 2011	Chess	civil servant	Suspension of the President by the International Federation -	March 2012
	17	Nov. 2011	Kayak	civil servant	Conflict between clubs and E.B	March 2012
	18	24 Nov. 2011	Rugby	civil servant	Conflict clubs and E.B	Dec 2012
	19	27 Nov. 2011	Volleyball	civil servant	Conflict clubs and E.B	Oct2012
	20	20 Oct. 2013	Basketball	civil servant	Conflict clubs and E-B	Dec 2014
	21	16 May 2014	Taekwondo	Sport personality	Conflict clubs and E-B	Dec 2014
	22	2015	Auto	civil servant	Conflict clubs and E-B	2015
	23	2016	Archery	civil servant	Conflict clubs and E-B	2017
	24	24 April 2019	Basketball	Official &Personality	Conflict clubs and E-B	20 Dec2020
	25	24 Apr. 2019	Sailing	civil servant	Conflict clubs and B-E	14Jan 2021
	26	24 Apr. 2019	Cricket	civil servant	Conflict clubs and B-E	Ongoing
	27	24 April 2019	Light aviation	civil servant	Conflict between clubs and B-E	Ongoing

Source: "Author

B. Provisional committees under the new law 30-09

Nevertheless, the application of the repealed article was often criticized as a source of conflict and misunderstanding between the public authorities and the national and international Olympic and sports movement.

It is with this in mind that the new law will propose a new formula that satisfies the Olympic and sports movement in the first place, while at the same time leaving some room for maneuver in the hands of the Administration. Thus, the old abrogated article will be split into two, the first one, article 26, stipulates that:

"Authorization may be withdrawn from any sports federation in the event of failure to comply with the operating rules laid down by its statutes or of violation of the legislation and regulations applicable to it."

This article constitutes a form of sanction against the federation which will be deprived of its accreditation, a sine qua non condition for receiving all forms of subsidies and donations necessary for its survival as provided for by the law (Art 82). Without this being able to call into question its legitimacy. It must be recognized that the vast majority of sports federations cannot implement their program without the support of the State. This constitutes an efficient weapon to impose the Administration's choices on the sport movement.

Article 31 stipulates that *"in case of serious violation by the federation of its statutes or of the legislation and regulations applicable to it or when the functioning or activities of the federation are prejudicial to the sport concerned, the administration may dissolve the federal governing body and take all useful measures in the interest of the sport concerned and in particular appoint a provisional committee whose mission is to ensure the management of the federation until the meeting of the general assembly whose date is fixed by the provisional committee within a maximum period of three months from the date of dissolution of the federation concerned."*

It should be noted that the legislator has taken over the content of the former repealed article (Art. 22), but has introduced the following two changes:

to send a formal notice to the governing body concerned to restore the situation within a period of three weeks

reduce the duration of the Provisional Committee's mandate to only three months instead of one year.

This arrangement, which can be described as intelligent, confirms the legislator's desire to reduce the degree of state intervention by avoiding recourse to the dissolution of an elected body, thus avoiding the outcry from civil society and international sports bodies.

C. Various scenarios for the constitution of the provisional committee

The legislator, either in the repealed Article 22 or in the current text, has remained silent on this point, leaving the Minister of Sport free to decide when to apply the provisions of this article and also on the nature of the composition of the provisional committee.

Nevertheless, a review of the chronology of the creation of provisional committees allows us to identify the path taken by the public authorities, opting for:

- The appointment of civil servants from the sports department.
- The appointment of personalities with material or symbolic power.
- The appointment of a mixed group chaired by a personality and accompanied by civil servants.

However, it should be noted that recourse to personalities with a reputation in society is often used when it concerns a large federation (Athletics 1992 / Football 1994 / Athletics 2000...), however when it concerns a small federation, the ministry calls on its own officials (Fencing 2000, Canoeing 2011, Sailing 2019...)

The adopted criteria for the distinction between a large and a small federation are: the influence of the sport both nationally and internationally, the budget allocated, the degree of popularity and the number of participants.

In the same vein, the absence of the CNOM, as a national sport actor, in the management of these conflicts should be noted, giving way to the ministry in charge to take the decisions relating to the provisional committees alone. Although law 30-09 stipulates in article 24 that among the attributions devolved to the CNOM "to undertake any conciliation action on the occasion of litigations opposing licensees, associations, federations and leagues at the request of one of the parties, to protect and exploit in accordance with the rules of the IOC and its instructions the Olympic symbols."

D. Missions of the provisional committee

The duties of the provisional committee generally consist of:

- carrying out an analysis of the financial, administrative and technical situation of the federation in order to highlight the grey areas and uncertainties and propose a recovery plan;
- clearing the arrears of the former bureau and to become the official interlocutor with the competent national and international bodies;
- carrying out a census of the members and clubs and to ensure their conformity with the texts of law in force;
- elaborating the national and international competition program and to ensure the adhesion of all the clubs and to see to its implementation;
- drawing up the draft general statutes of the federation and to propose their amendment at an extraordinary general assembly;
- creating favorable conditions for the holding of an elective general assembly of the new board.

E. Duration of the provisional committee work

The legislator, in the previous text, set the maximum period of one year for the work of the provisional committee, while in the new law this period has been reduced to three months only, and it seems logical that any act or decision taken beyond this period will be considered as null and void.

Table 2: Duration of the work of provisional committees (according to the repealed law 06-87)

Duration of the Provisional Committee Sporting	discipline
4 years	Football
1 year	Handball
4 years	Athletics
4 years	Football
4 years	Cycling
3 years Handball	
6 years	Athletics
1 year	Fencing
1 year	Wrestling

Source: "Author

Nevertheless, past experience shows that this time limit is rarely respected, particularly for federations with a high profile.

For example, the disqualification of the national football team in the first round of the 1994 World Cup led to the appointment of a provisional committee chaired by General Hosni Bnslimane. This committee largely exceeded the duration required by Article 22, namely one year, and continued to work for four years in total illegality. The pretext always put forward to justify this overstay is that the discipline is faced with major international events that require total mobilization, which automatically postpones the question of electing a new bureau to a later date.

The distinction already made between small and large federations can be applied once again to the working time of the provisional committees. The federations managed by civil servants generally respect the one-year time limit, while the second category largely exceeds the time limit prescribed in the law and can continue to manage the sport for three to seven years in "total illegality".

Table 3: Duration of the provisional committees (according to the current law 30-09)

Duration of the provisional Sporting committee	discipline
16 months	Sailing
16 months	Basketball
16 months	Light aviation
16 months	Cricket

Source: "Author

F. Divergent reactions to the interim committee

As mentioned earlier, the appointment of a provisional committee is essentially the result of the emergence of thorny problems within these sports bodies. Similarly, recourse to the application of article 31 of law 30-09 is ultimately only the last step after all avenues of conciliation and good offices between the warring parties have been exhausted.

And given that the federal body is split between different clans, it is normal that reactions to the appointment of the provisional committee differ from one clan to another.

The reaction of the opposition clan within the federation is one of unconditional support in the form of cooperation and respect for the decisions taken by the provisional committee, including the implementation of the sports competition program. However, this tactic is only momentary as it will change with the approach of the elections of the new board.

The second clan, described as neutral, is made up of a heterogeneous number of clubs that are geographically far apart and whose performance in competitions is modest. Nevertheless, their votes will be very much in demand by the candidates for the elections of the new board.

As for the third clan, made up of the members of the former board who suffered from the decision to appoint a provisional committee, they will use all the means at their disposal to discredit the actions carried out by this committee by boycotting sports activities, by organizing other activities in parallel and by writing to the international sports authorities to denounce this interference by the public authorities, thus giving the impression that they do not recognize this provisional committee.

G. The difficult transition to a modern mode of governance

It is clear that the use of provisional committees as a means of direct management of a federation's affairs by the ministry in charge will be frequently used in the mid-1990s and at the beginning of the third millennium. This can be explained by the fact that this decade constitutes a break between two modes of management.

The first traditional one, based on the principle of voluntary work, is characterized by the fact that the president has a special status and discretionary power, he is also irremovable and the idea is often circulated that "sport for sportsmen", which means that the sportsman, given his mastery of the technical aspect, is the most qualified to become a trainer and then a leader.

As for the second period, which coincided with the promulgation of the law on physical education and sports, new concepts closely linked to the modern management of private companies appeared. From now on, sports activity, with the good performances of athletes, will be considered as a lever of the economy that can drain money and attract investors. However, the existing structures are so archaic that they cannot keep up with the requirements of this new context; worse, they may constitute an obstacle to their implementation.

It should be noted that the transition from a traditional management mode to a modern one will not be easy and will give rise to confrontations between the two mentalities. Similarly, new stakeholders will surface and demand to be involved in the decision-making process, which was previously the exclusive domain of the president.

H. Contested results of the interim committees

It seems legitimate to ask what the achievements of the interim committees have been and whether their intervention has eradicated or at least reduced the scale of the conflict and crisis within the federation.

Another important question is whether the federations are unable to carry out the functions assigned to them without the constant intervention of the public authorities?

First of all, it is imperative to point out that the evaluation reports from the heads of the provisional committees reveal multiple dysfunctions, including, for example: traditional and individual management closely linked to the president, who has broad discretionary power and is often irremovable, in the absence of a procedure manual.

Table 4: Sports disciplines that have been managed more than once by the provisional committee

The sport discipline	Designation of the 1st committee	Designation of the 2nd committee	Designation of the 3rd committee
Football	1983	1994	
Handball	1991	1996	
Athletics	1992	2000	
Cycling	1996	2006	
Fencing	2000	2003	
Basketball	1983	2013	2019

Source: "Author

It should also be noted, after an analysis of past experiences, that direct management by provisional committees is not a guarantee that problems and conflicts will disappear. Some federations have been managed more than once by provisional committees. To say that the problems are so deep-rooted in culture and mentality that the only remedy is a long-term effort to raise awareness, train and persuade.

This situation highlights the fact that the cornerstone of any expected reform lies essentially in the mode of governance of the federation's affairs, and in particular the difficulties encountered in applying the mechanisms of a democratic election of the federation's bodies, which may explain this permanent recourse to the intervention of public authorities.

V. Conclusion

Throughout this article, we have raised the question of power within organizations, by treating, as a case study, the provisional committees appointed by the ministry in charge of sport to replace an elected federal bureau. The interviews conducted with MSSO officials suggest that, in order to avoid these situations of conflict, legal and managerial reforms should be introduced into the governance of sports organizations, while ensuring that the democratic gains are preserved against any possible deviation.

With regard to the first aspect, it is imperative to revise Article 31 by promulgating an application text that precisely determines the cases requiring recourse to the provisional committee. In order to enlighten, on the one hand, the sporting public opinion on the true intentions of the legislator and to avoid the multitude of interpretations, and on the other hand to adapt this text to the new challenges and constraints of a context in perpetual change.

At present, a serious debate is taking place in the sports arena concerning the degree of conformity of Article 31 with the Kingdom's Constitution, which was promulgated in July 2011, and in particular its Article 12.

Therefore, It is suggested that inspiration be drawn from the recasting of the organic law relating to local authorities in Morocco in July 2015, as it abolished the concept of tutelage and replaced it with the concept of control. Thus, the question of the dissolution of a collective elected office is no longer within the competence of the Governor, as it was before, it is entrusted to the judicial authority. It is in this sense that article 63 of this organic law stipulates that only the judiciary is competent to deal with the dismissal of council members, the declaration of nullity of deliberations of the council of the municipality as well as the suspension of the execution of deliberations and decrees tainted by legal defects, subject to the provisions of article 117 of this organic law. Only the judiciary is competent to dissolve the council of the commune.

The power of substitution according to the organic law, which will be detailed in articles 21/72/73/76, will no longer be in the hands of the public authorities but will be subject to the prior approval of the judicial authority.

As for the second part of the reform proposals, it essentially concerns the managerial side of the federation by making an effort to strengthen the capacities of the managers by providing its structures with human, material and informational resources so that they can assume the attributions that have been devolved to them.

It should also be noted, in the light of past experience, that on the eve of the elective general assembly of a new board, the provisional committee quickly withdraws from the sports scene, thus leaving the field open to the improvisation of a newly elected team on the basis of a tacit arrangement between its members. However, this fragile structure cannot, given the inadequacy of its resources and the modesty of its accumulated experience, meet all the expectations and promises made at every turn before the General Assembly, which will automatically lead to disruptions and the resignation of certain members who disapprove of the management method applied.

In order to avoid such problems, it is advisable that the transfer of power takes place during a transitional period during which the members of this committee continue to provide help and assistance to the new bureau. In addition to that, the supervisory department is called upon to apply the technique of monitoring the actions of the new bureau more closely in order to prevent it from repeating the same mistakes of the very recent past.

References

- [1.] J.L.Chaplet, "Autonomie du Sport en Europe" collection Politiques et pratiques sportives éd : Conseil de l'Europe. 2010
- [2.] M. Crozier., E. Friedberg. "L'acteur et le système :Les contraintes de l'action collective". Paris : Editions du Seuil, 1^{ere} éd. 1977.
- [3.] V. Dubois, "La sociologie de l'action publique De la sociohistoire à l'observation des pratiques". Publié dans "Historicité de l'action publique. 2003.
- [4.] A.Elakari, "Le Cadre Juridique du Sport au Maroc". Revue REMALD.n°111, 2013
- [5.] P.Hassenteufel.): "Sociologie politique l'action publique. Paris : Armand Colin, coll. «U Sociologie". 2008
- [6.] McClellandLe pouvoir, In «déterminant de la motivation », Psybernétique, 2001. 218 ModenpoliticalAnalysis, 2eme édition. 1970.
- [7.] P.Morin,Le management et le pouvoir. Éditions d'Organisation, Université, Paris. 1991.

- [8.] R.Hocine, *Stratégies de conquête du pouvoir et mouvement sportif associatif dans un Etat d'Afrique du nord en mutation Les trajectoires des personnalités entre sport et politique du niveau local au niveau national en Algérie*. En vue d'obtenir le doctorat de Sciences et techniques des activités physiques et sportives/ Université de Bordeaux. Juillet 2020.
- [9.] J-R.Galbraith, *Designing complex organizations*. Wesley: Reading, Addison.1973.
- [10.] J-C. Thoenig, P. Duran. "L'État et la gestionpubliqueterritoriale". In: *Revue française de science politique*, 46^e année, n°4. 1996. pp. 580-623.
- [11.] Commission of the European Communities. *White Paper on Sport*. Brussels. 2007.